

1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of liver metastasis: PTPN9.**

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6 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the liver is a frequent complication
7 of both breast cancer and colorectal cancer, among the two most common cancers that afflict man (1-5).
8 We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially
9 expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to
10 the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in
11 the liver metastases of humans with breast cancer, comparing the liver metastatic transcriptome to the
12 primary tumor transcriptome. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and
13 up-regulation upon metastasis to the liver, PTPN9, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical
14 management of liver metastasis.
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1 We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the
2 transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes
3 the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary
4 tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of
5 NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the
6 lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in
7 metastasis to the liver to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the
8 liver metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and
9 metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: PTPN9.

6 Results

7 **Figure 1:** PTPN9 is differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

8 I. Liver metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

9 $n=19$ primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

10 $n=27$ liver metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100138852_TGI_at	9.29E-03	-2.72	-2.874481	-6.14E-01	PTPN9	3205/52378	93.9

13 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in liver
14 metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of protein tyrosine
15 phosphatase, non-receptor type 9, encoded by *PTPN9* in metastasis to the liver in humans with breast
16 cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of PTPN9 changed more than nearly 95% of the human liver metastatic
17 transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 52,378
18 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PTPN9 messenger
19 RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of PTPN9 during disease progression and
20 dissemination in breast cancer.

18 Discussion

19 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
20 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
21 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of PTPN9, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity
22 and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with liver metastasis who have failed
23 previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of liver metastasis in
24 humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose
25 metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase
26 approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the
27 daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding
28 cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone
resistance (11).

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Methods

We utilized GSE56493 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE124647 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.